

STUDY OF FRAGMENTATION OF BIS-CARBAMATE MEE-2 INTO FRAGMENT IONS IN THE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTRUM

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Abstract. In this research work, the mass spectra of *N, N'*-hexamethylene-bis-[(*m*-cresolyl)-carbamate], i.e. MEE-2, were studied. During the fragmentation of bis-carbamate, ions such as *m*-methylphenyl, hexamethylenediamine, carbamate and others appeared. As a result, ions were identified that proved the elemental composition, molecular weight, chemical bonds, brutto and structural formula of MEE-2 bis-carbamate.

Keywords: bis-carbamate, amine, hexamethylene, fragmentation, spectrum, bond, ions, molecule, atom, structure.

Introduction. Molecules containing the carbamate group play an important role in the development of modern drugs, medicines and chemicals. Carbamate and bis-carbamate derivatives are widely used in agricultural chemicals such as pesticides, fungicides, acaricides and herbicides [1]. They also play an important role in the chemical and paint industries as starting materials, intermediates and solvents [2].

The authors of this article synthesized bis-carbamates of the MEE series. Also, physicochemical, biological and pharmacological parameters were studied and used in various branches of the chemical industry [3-5]. Below is the linear and three-dimensional structure of bis-carbamate MEE-2 (Figure 1):

Figure 1. *N, N'*-hexamethylene-bis-[(*m*-cresolyl)-carbamate], i.e. MEE-2

The purpose of this research work is to study the structure of *N, N'*-hexamethylene-bis-[(*m*-cresolyl)-carbamate], i.e. MEE-2 with use mass spectroscopic method.

Materials and Methods. Chromato-mass spectrum of *N, N'*-hexamethylene bis-[(*m*-cresolyl)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2 on an Agilent Technologies 6420 spectrometer, APCI METHOD C118-brand column, 5% phenylmethylsilicone liquid phase, control parameters 500 °C initial temperatures ranging from 150 °C to 320 °C were obtained with an Agilent Technologies 9973 inert mass spectrometer.

Results and Discussions. In the chromato-mass spectrum of *N, N'*-hexamethylene bis-[(*m*-cresolyl)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2, the formation of ions corresponding to their molecular mass and the mass of fragment ions resulting from their fragmentation was determined (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Chromato-mass spectrum of N,N'-hexamethylene bis-[(meta-cresolyl)-carbamate] i.e. MEE-2

In this case, the molecular ion peak of MEE-2 was equal to 383.8. Above is the chromato-mass spectrum of fragment ions formed from the initial MEE-2 molecular ion (Fig. 2). In addition, in the spectrum, mass m/z 249, m/z 135, m/z 91, in the second direction, m/z 234, m/z 100, in the third direction, m/z 293, m/z 249, formation of fragment ions with m/z 202, m/z 158, m/z 114 and m/z 59 was determined.

After the MEE-2 substance was included in the chromato-mass spectrum, a bis-carbamate molecular ion with m/z 383 was formed in 0.711 minutes under the selected conditions. In turn, the MEE-2 ion with m/z 249 from the release of the m/z 135 radical in one direction at 0.183 minutes from the bis-carbamate ion:

In the second direction, the MEE-2 ion with m/z 234 splits off at 0.192 minutes with m/z 150 radical:

In the third direction, the separation of MEE-2 ions with m/z 293 from the release of the *m*-methylphenyl radical at 0.185 minutes was shown:

In the chromato-mass spectrum, fragment ions formed from molecular ions also form small ion fragments. The m/z 249 ion formed from MEE-2 separated from itself the hexamethylenediamine radical with m/z 115 to form the ion with m/z 135:

The resulting m/z 135 ion separated from itself a carbon dioxide molecule with m/z 44 and formed an ion with m/z 91:

The ion formed in the second direction of the initial MEE-2 ion separates the m/z 135 radical from it and forms an ion with m/z 100:

The m/z 293 ion formed in the third direction of the molecular ion of MEE-2, in its turn, disintegrates in two directions. In the first direction, m/z 44 separates carbon dioxide and forms an ion with m/z 249:

The second m -methylphenyl radical with m/z 91 is separated from the m/z 249 ion, forming the N,N -hexamethylene bis-carbamate ion with m/z 202:

The resulting m/z 202 N,N-hexamethylene bis-carbamate ion separates from itself a m/z 44 carbon dioxide molecule and forms an ion with m/z 158:

The m/z 158 ion also fragmented in two directions. In the first direction, he separated the hexamethylenamine radical with m/z 99 from itself and formed the carbamate ion with m/z 59:

In the second direction, it separated carbon dioxide m/z 44 from itself and formed N,N-hexamethylenediamine ion with m/z 114:

The above listed fragments of the MEE-2 molecule prove the composition, structure and brutto formula of the synthesized bis-carbamate.

Conclusion. Upon fragmentation of the N,N'-hexamethylene-bis-[(m-cresolyl)-carbamate] molecule, i.e. MEE-2 chromatography-mass spectroscopy method identified ions such as m-methylphenyl, hexamethylenediamine, carbon dioxide, N,N-hexamethylene bis-carbamate, carbamate itself and others. These fragments prove the structure of bis-carbamate MEE-2.

REFERENCES

1. Arun K. Ghosh and Margherita Brindisi Organic Carbamates in Drug Design and Medicinal Chemistry Med. Chem. 2015, 58, 7, 2895–2940 Publication Date: January 7, 2015 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm501371s>.
2. Куликова Н. А., Лебедева Г. Ф.. Гербициды и экологические аспекты их применения. – М.: «Либроком», 2010. — 152 с.
3. Махсумов А.Г., Машаев Э.Э., Холбоев Ю.Х., Уразов Ф.Б., Зоҳиджонов С.А. N,N'-гексаметилен бис [(м-крезолило) -карбамат] и его физико-химические свойства // Life Sciences and Agriculture. 2022. №1 (9), С. 7-11.
4. Сафаров Т.Т., Махсумов А.Г., Машаев Э.Э., Кодиров О.О. Синтез N,N'-гексаметилен бис-[(орто-крезолило) -карбамата] и изучение физико-химических параметров // Композиционные материалы. 2022. №4. С.47-50.
5. Машаев Э.Э., Махсумов А.Г., Исмаилов Б.М., Мухиддинов Б.Ф. Нефт маҳсулотлари асосида N,N'-гексаметилен бис [(мета-крезолило)-карбамат] синтези ва қўлланилиши «O'ZBEKISTON NEFT VA GAZ JURNALI» –Т., №1/2023. С.35-38.